

ЕКОНОМІЧНІ ПРОБЛЕМИ РОЗВИТКУ ГАЛУЗЕЙ ТА ВИДІВ ЕКОНОМІЧНОЇ ДІЯЛЬНОСТІ

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Formation of marketing product policy of agricultural enterprises

The subject of the research there are theoretical foundations for the formation of the marketing policy of agrarian enterprises.

The purpose there is a study of the essence, role, directions of formation and implementation of marketing commodity policy of agrarian enterprises.

Research methods. The work uses a dialectical method of scientific knowledge, analysis and synthesis, a systematic approach, a method of comparing and summarizing data.

Results of work. The article defines the essence, structure and features of marketing commodity policy of agrarian enterprises. The relationship between the economic efficiency of the sale of agricultural products and the management of the marketing commodity policy of agricultural enterprises has been established. The directions for the formation and implementation of the marketing commodity policy of agrarian enterprises have been determined.

Field of application. Marketing.

Conclusions. It was determined that the marketing of products of agricultural enterprises is somewhat more complicated than other types of marketing, which is due to the variety of means of its implementation, the transformation of the modern paradigm of agricultural marketing. An analysis of the overall product policy of the product policy of an agricultural enterprise was carried out, the components of which are the consumer value of agricultural products, the economic benefits of the agricultural producer from the production and sale of products, the characteristics of the trademark for certain types of agricultural products and their packaging, the effectiveness of the introduction of types of agricultural products into the markets, the indicators of the assortment and its balance from the standpoint of the life cycle of agricultural products. The research established that the objects for further planning of the product policy of agricultural enterprises are the analysis of marketing components of agricultural products and methods of analysis of the product portfolio, assortment and nomenclature of products of an agricultural enterprise.

Key words: marketing, marketing product policy, marketing activity, efficiency, management of marketing activity.

Формування маркетингової товарної політики аграрних підприємств

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні засади формування маркетингової політики аграрних підприємств.

Метою дослідження є дослідження сутності, ролі, напрямів формування та реалізації маркетингової товарної політики аграрних підприємств.

Методи дослідження. У роботі використані діалектичний метод наукового пізнання, аналіз та синтез, системний підхід, метод порівняння та узагальнення даних.

Результати роботи. У статті визначено сутність, структуру та особливості маркетингової товарної політики аграрних підприємств. Встановлено взаємозв'язок між економічною ефективністю реалізації аграрної продукції та управлінням маркетинговою товарною політикою аграрних підприємств. Визначено напрямки формування та реалізації маркетингової товарної політики аграрних підприємств.

Галузь застосування. Маркетинг.

Висновки. Визначено, що маркетинг продукції аграрних підприємств дещо складніший від інших видів маркетингу, що обумовлено різноманітністю засобів його впровадження, трансформацією сучасної парадигми аграрного маркетингу. Проведено аналіз системи товарної політики аграрного підприємства складовими якого є споживча цінність аграрної продукції, економічні вигоди агровиробника від випуску та реалізації продукції, характеристики товарної марки для окремих видів аграрної продукції та її упаковки, ефективність впровадження видів аграрної продукції на ринках, показники асортименту та його збалансованість з позицій життєвого циклу аграрної продукції. Дослідженням встановлено, що об'єктами для подальшого планування товарної політики аграрних підприємств є аналіз маркетингових складових аграрної продукції та методи аналізу товарного портфелю, асортименту і номенклатури продукції аграрного підприємства.

Ключові слова: маркетинг, маркетингова товарна політика, маркетингова діяльність, ефективність, управління маркетинговою діяльністю.

Formulation of the problem. The commodity policy of agricultural enterprises involves strategic and tactical actions based on predetermined principles of market behavior, the formation of an assortment of agricultural products and its management, taking into account the specifics of the agricultural sector of the economy. Any enterprise in the agricultural sector must analyze the factors that influence the formation of product policy and implement it as accurately as possible in conditions of fierce competition, focusing on the demand and expectations of consumers.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Theoretical and methodological aspects of the formation and implementation of the marketing commodity policy were studied by such well-known foreign and domestic scientists as G. Armstrong, D. Anker, P.R. Dixon, F. Kotler, M.Yu. Antonchenko, V.V. Arestenko, L.V. Balabanova, O.Yu. Bilenkyi, S.M. Bonyar, A.V. Vojchak, S.S. Harkavenko,

I.A. Gogol, E.V. , R. Coles, R. Kramer, Krykavskiy, N.O. Krykovtseva, N.V. Kortielova, Zh.Zh. Lamben, T. Levitt, Ya.S. Larina, A.F. Pavlenko, G.O. Peresadko, A.J. Strickland, A.A. Thompson, N.B. Tkachenko, I.A. Tkachuk, G.O. Cold and others. However, certain methodological and practical aspects regarding the determination of the mutual influence of the specifics of the activity of agrarian enterprises on the formation of marketing commodity policy are not sufficiently substantiated.

The purpose of the article there is a study of the essence, role, directions of formation and implementation of marketing commodity policy of agrarian enterprises.

Presentation of the main material of the study. Marketing related to the production and sale of agricultural products is much more complicated than other types of marketing: this complexity is due to the variety of methods and ways of its implementation. The use of special methods of

planning and implementation of marketing activities is due to a significant number of various products on the agro-food market, some differentiation of products and their significance for the consumer [1, p. 153].

A large number of domestic and foreign scientists were engaged in the study and analytical activities of marketing commodity policy, who defined its components in different ways and accordingly differentiated the process of analysis and further planning of marketing commodity policy.

The transformation of marketing management, that is, the transition from the sales to the innovative marketing concept of management of an agricultural enterprise, involves the coordination of the marketing system of the enterprise not only with the external environment, but also with other spheres of enterprise management [2].

The analysis of the commodity policy of enterprises can be aimed at [3, p. 46]:

- assessment of the results and benefits of the subject of entrepreneurial activity from the sale of a certain product, product lines and product range;
- analysis of the attitude of consumers towards the goods of the agricultural enterprise and the goods of the respective competitors;
- analysis of associations related to these goods;
- study of the opportunities and threats of the macro environment, as well as the strengths and weaknesses of the product;
- assessment of feasibility and effectiveness of the process of development and introduction of new products of agrarian enterprises to the market;
- clarification of the consistency of the product range with the goals of the enterprise and its balance in view of the life cycle of the products;
- monitoring the attitude of various market subjects to the structural elements of the product, developing measures to improve it and optimizing the product range.

Solving the above tasks requires defining the object and subject of analysis. The objects of commodity policy analysis in general are:

- commodity unit and elements of its structure (characteristics, branding, packaging);
- product line and product range;
- a new product (service) of the enterprise and the process of its development.

The subject of the analysis of the commodity policy of an agricultural enterprise is [3, p. 55]:

- consumer value of agricultural products;
 - economic benefits of an agrarian enterprise from the production and sale of agricultural products;
 - product brand characteristics for certain types of products (popularity; consumer loyalty; cost, etc.) and its packaging;
 - effectiveness of introduction of new products on the markets;
 - indicators of the assortment and its balance from the point of view of the life cycle of the product.
- The marketing policy of agricultural enterprises must take into account certain factors [4, c. 71]:
- the formation of demand occurs under the influence of deterministic or stochastic needs, requests and interests, therefore, the system of marketing planning and effective marketing product policy must necessarily and first of all satisfy the primary needs of consumers;
 - production processes, storage of agricultural products depend on natural and weather conditions;
 - peculiarities of the formation of demand for agricultural products – seasonality and low elasticity;
 - the formation of a set of goods that could be operated, ensuring that the goods are alternately brought to the market at the peak of demand growth, its maintenance and removal from the market, taking into account seasonality;
 - the complexity of changes in the range of Ukrainian products;
 - minimal opportunities and limitations of agricultural producers in diversification solutions.

Having analyzed the theoretical aspects of the marketing commodity policy of agrarian enterprises and the prerequisites for its formation, it would be appropriate, in our opinion, to define and characterize its main functions.

The functions of marketing commodity policy of agricultural enterprises should reflect the specifics of agricultural marketing planning, development and implementation of commodity policy. In general, it is advisable to divide the functions of marketing product policy into preliminary (strategic) and main (tactical) ones [5, p. 48].

The strategic functions of the marketing commodity policy of agricultural enterprises include:

- identification of a specific segment of the market, determination of the place of agricultural products manufactured (grown) among the total set of products and services on the market of agricultural products, analysis of the specifics of this segment;

- analysis of the rationality of overcoming market barriers;
- analysis of the agricultural market situation, study and forecasting of market demand and supply in quantitative volumes in a specific season;
- development of the concept of the life cycle of agricultural products;
- mandatory systematic monitoring of the marketing environment of agricultural enterprises;
- determining the competitiveness of agricultural products, ways to increase it;
- analysis of the possibilities of maximizing the volume of production of agricultural products and reducing their cost and price.

The main functions of the marketing product policy of agricultural enterprises include: planning the production process, organization of material and technical support, management of marketing innovation policy, management of the quality and competitiveness of agricultural products, ensuring the quality of the product corresponding to consumer demand, assortment management, bringing the product to the market and its support, monitoring the performance of tasks, etc.

On the basis of the above, it is advisable to single out several areas of analytical work and determine the most effective and acceptable for further use in the context of the analysis of the commodity policy of agrarian enterprises. It is appropriate to make the main objects of analysis and further planning of the commodity policy of agricultural enterprises [6, p. 109]:

1. Analysis of the marketing components of agricultural products, the value of these products for the consumer, loyalty to the brand, comparison of agricultural products with similar products of competing companies, comparison of product properties from the standpoint of the agricultural enterprise and buyers, analysis of the novelty and innovativeness of products, analysis of the brand, packaging (containers), housing, economic benefits of agricultural enterprises from the production of a particular type of agricultural products, in-depth assessment of the needs of individual groups of consumers.

2. Methods of analysis of the product portfolio, assortment and nomenclature, their balance from the standpoint of the life cycle of the product and agricultural enterprise.

Let's consider in more detail the elements of the analysis of marketing components. For an enter-

prise, the product is primarily a source of profit, an agricultural enterprise is no exception, therefore its analysis involves giving priority to such economic criteria as the volume of sales, seasonality of profits; level and dynamics of profitability; the amount and dynamics of sales of agricultural products (depending on the season); market share of the enterprise in the agricultural market. The main list of indicators for the analysis of the economic performance of products is given in the table.

From the point of view of marketing, the economic goals of the agricultural enterprise will be satisfied only if the needs of the buyers are satisfied. Therefore, the marketing analysis of agricultural products (services) should begin with the study of its consumer value. It means not only objective consumer value, which can be expressed, for example, by technical parameters, but also subjective consumer value of products, as well as actual and potential consumer value. The buyer is the main object for an agricultural enterprise, but this does not mean that the analysis of agricultural products should be limited only to the study of its consumer value for the buyer.

The analysis should take into account the opinion of other subjects of the agricultural market who are interested in the agricultural products of the enterprise. The analysis must necessarily have a reference point, for example: products of competing companies, other ways of satisfying needs, etc. No less important is the temporal aspect, which should take into account the analysis of agricultural products in the past, current and future time, which makes it possible to see the assessment of dynamics and the qualitative nature of changes, establish trends, and make appropriate forecasts for the future [7, 8].

When analyzing agricultural products, it is necessary to consider its various parameters and functions, therefore it should be multifaceted. The method of analysis depends on the type of agricultural products (crop or livestock products), market, enterprise, time period. Parameters such as sales markets, sales periods and seasonality are of particular importance in the analysis of agricultural products.

In general terms, it can be stated that the purpose of the analysis of the marketing commodity policy of agricultural enterprises is to assess the conformity of agricultural products with the economic expectations of the producing enterprise,

Indicators for analyzing the economic performance of agricultural products

Indicator	Definition
Sales volume (physical unit)	Cumulative number of implemented units of agricultural production
Gross income (UAH)	The product of the total quantity of sold units of agricultural products and the price of a unit of production (aggregate revenue)
Profit (UAH)	The difference between total revenue and total costs
Profitability units of agricultural products (UAH)	The difference between the unit price product and its cost price production
Marginal profit (%)	The ratio of the difference between the price units of agricultural production and variable costs in the calculation of unit of production to the unit price products
Breakeven level sales of agricultural products (%)	The ratio of fixed costs to marginal profit
Market share of the agricultural enterprise in the segment of this product category (%)	The ratio of the volume of sales of agricultural products to the total market sales
Sales growth (physics unit)	The difference between the volume of sales for certain period to the base volume sales

Source: created by authors and data [1, 3, 4, 6]

the needs of the agricultural market, and to identify opportunities and threats to the functioning of an agricultural enterprise in a competitive environment. On the basis of the conducted analysis, decisions regarding the improvement of agricultural production are substantiated.

For entrepreneurial activity in the agrarian sphere, a necessary indicator of effective functioning is the value of agricultural products. The issue of analysis and development of the marketing commodity policy of an agricultural enterprise directly depends on the analysis of the value of agricultural products [9, p. 239].

The next important element of the analysis of the marketing product policy of an agricultural enterprise and its products as its key element is the method of analyzing the consumer value of products by buyers. According to the concept of marketing, an agricultural enterprise should produce (grow) not what it can or has produced (grow) before, but what consumers need. Agricultural products have many properties, the most important of which are their consumer value for the buyer, the rank of this consumer value, as well as the characteristic of the product that is decisive when making a purchase. Assessment of the significant property of agricultural products, combined with the need to purchase it for the consumer, and therefore the significance for the economic results of the agricultural enterprise [10, p. 26].

Another method of analyzing agricultural products is the analysis of the benefits created at the agricultural enterprise from the production (growing) of

products. Evaluating agricultural products through the lens of consumer value and customer expectations means finding out the requirements that an ideal product should meet. The data is obtained as a result of marketing research. Often, the necessary information is obtained with the help of employees who maintain constant contact with customers. However, the perceptions of employees about the attitude of buyers to agricultural products do not always correspond to reality, and therefore it is advisable to conduct a comparative analysis of data obtained from employees of agricultural enterprises and intermediate or final buyers.

Analyzing any agricultural enterprise, one can easily single out among the product nomenclature and annual financial reports and reports of marketing and analytical centers a group of agricultural products that satisfy the requirements of end consumers and bring economic profit from their production and sale.

Conclusions

Marketing of products of agricultural enterprises of Ukraine is somewhat more complicated than other types of marketing, which is due to the variety of means of its implementation, the transformation of the modern paradigm of agricultural marketing. The application of various methods of planning and implementation of marketing activities of agricultural enterprises is determined by the characteristics of various types of products on the agricultural market, their significance for the end

consumer and the characteristics of marketing in the agricultural sector.

The subject of the analysis of the commodity policy of the agricultural enterprise is the consumer value of agricultural products, the economic benefits of the agricultural producer from the production and sale of products, the characteristics of the trademark for certain types of agricultural products and their packaging, the effectiveness of the introduction of types of agricultural products to the markets, the indicators of the assortment and its balance from the standpoint of the life cycle of the agricultural products

The main objects of analysis and further planning of the product policy of agricultural enterprises are: 1) analysis of the marketing components of agricultural products, their value for the consumer, the attitude of consumers to the brand, comparison of agricultural products with products of competing companies, comparison of product properties from the perspective of the company and buyers, analysis of the novelty and innovativeness of agricultural products, analysis of brand, packaging (container), ХЦ, economic benefits of an agricultural enterprise from the production of a separate agricultural product, an in-depth assessment of the needs of individual groups of consumers; 2) methods of analysis of the product portfolio, assortment and nomenclature, their balance from the standpoint of the life cycle of the product and the enterprise.

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